

COMPLETE INTEGRABLE VECTOR FIELD GEOMETRY

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Abstract. This article is the result of research on operations on integrable vector fields on the plane, namely: finding their integral lines, finding the Lie bracket and finding the flow.

Keywords: Integral line, vector field, vector field flow, Lie bracket (Lie commutator), integrable vector field, manifold, field, orbit.

ПОЛНАЯ ИНТЕГРИРУЕМАЯ ГЕОМЕТРИЯ ВЕКТОРНОГО ПОЛЯ

Аннотация. Эта статья является результатом исследования операций над интегрируемыми векторными полями на плоскости, а именно: нахождения их целых линий, нахождения скобки Ли и нахождения потока.

Ключевые слова: Интегральная прямая, векторное поле, поток векторного поля, скобка Ли (коммутатор Ли), интегрируемое векторное поле, многообразие, поле, орбита.

INTRODUCTION

Definition-1. Let M be a smooth manifold of dimension n , $T_x M$ be a tangent space at the point $x \in M$. The map P , which assigns to each point $x \in M$ some subspace $P(x) \subset T_x M$, is called a distribution. If $\dim P(x) = k$ for all $x \in M$, then P is called a k -dimensional distribution.

Definition-2. A distribution P is called smooth if for each point $x \in M$ there exists a neighborhood of this point $U(x)$, and smooth vector fields x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m given on $U(x)$, such that vectors $x_1(y), x_2(y), \dots, x_m(y)$ form a basis for subspaces $P(y)$ for each $y \in U(x)$.

Definition-3. A distribution P is called completely integrable if for every point $x \in M$ there exists a connected submanifold N_x of a manifold M containing a point x such that $T_x N_y = P(y)$ for all $y \in N_x$.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The submanifold N_x is called the integral submanifold of the distribution P .

If a family D of smooth vector fields is given, then a smooth distribution naturally arises. Indeed, if D consists of smooth vector fields, then for each point $x \in M$ the set of vectors $D(x) = \{X(x): X \in D\}$ generates some subspace $P_D(x)$ of the tangent space $T_x M$. Of course, the dimensions of the subspace $P_D(x)$ can vary from point to point. This distribution is denoted by P_D .

It is said that the vector field X belongs to the distribution P if $X(x) \in P(x)$ for all $x \in M$.

Recall that the distribution of P on a manifold M is called involutive if $X, Y \in P$, then $[X, Y] \in P$ holds.

RESULTS

A necessary and sufficient condition for the complete integrability of a distribution of constant dimension is given in Frobenius' theorem.

Frobenius' theorem. In order for the distribution P to be completely integrable, it is necessary and sufficient that it be involutive.

Definition-4. A family of vector fields D is called completely integrable if the corresponding P_D distribution generated by D is completely integrable.

Note that if the family D consists of a single vector field, then it is always completely integrable, since according to the theorem on the existence and uniqueness of the solution of a system of differential equations, a single integral curve of the vector field passes through each point. If a family consists of more than one vector field, then it is not always completely integrable.

The Frobenius theorem generalized by Herman for distributions of non-constant dimension gives a necessary and sufficient condition for the complete integrability of a family of vector fields consisting of a finite number of vector fields.

Theorems (Hermann). Let $D = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k\}$ be a family of finitely many vector fields on a manifold M . A family D is completely integrable if and only if it is involutive.

The involution of a family of vector fields $D = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k\}$ means the following: for any vector fields $X, Y \in D$, there exist smooth functions $f^l(x)$, $x \in M$, $l = 1, \dots, k$ such that

$$[X, Y] = \sum_{l=1}^k f^l(x) X_l$$

In the case when the family consists of an infinite number of vector fields, as the existing examples show, this theorem is incorrect.

We have proved the following theorem.

The theorem. Let $M = R^3$ be a Euclidean space with Cartesian coordinates x, y, z . A family D consisting of vector fields

$$X = y \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + x \frac{\partial}{\partial y},$$

$$Y = \frac{\partial}{\partial z},$$

generates a completely integrable distribution, integral manifolds which are hyperbolic cylinders, half-planes and straight.

Example. For a function

$$H(x, y, z) = \frac{x^2}{4} + \frac{y^2}{3} - \frac{z^2}{5}$$

the corresponding Hamiltonian vector field has the following form

$$H_x = \frac{x}{2} \quad H_y = \frac{2y}{3}$$

The corresponding Hamiltonian system has the following form

$$X_H = H_x \frac{\partial}{\partial y} - H_y \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Rightarrow X_H = \frac{x}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} - \frac{2y}{3} \frac{\partial}{\partial x}$$

$$X_H = \left\{ -\frac{2y}{3}, \frac{x}{2}, 0 \right\}$$

$$Y = \{4y, -3x, 0\}$$

$$[X_H, Y]^i = \sum_{j=1}^3 (X_j \frac{\partial Y_i}{\partial x_j} - Y_j \frac{\partial X_i}{\partial x_j})$$

$$[X_H, Y]^1 = 0 \quad [X_H, Y]^2 = 0 \quad [X_H, Y]^3 = 0$$

$$[X_H, Y] = 0 \quad X_H = \left\{ -\frac{2y}{3}, \frac{x}{2}, 0 \right\}$$

$$x(0) = x_0 \quad y(0) = y_0 \quad z(0) = z_0$$

The trajectories of which are circles:

$$\begin{cases} x = x^0 \cos 2\sqrt{3}t + \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \cdot y^0 \sin 2\sqrt{3}t \\ y = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} x^0 \sin 2\sqrt{3}t + y^0 \cos 2\sqrt{3}t \\ z = 0 \end{cases}$$

Vector field flow:

$$\begin{cases} x = x \cos 2\sqrt{3}t + \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \cdot y \sin 2\sqrt{3}t \\ y = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} x \sin 2\sqrt{3}t + y \cos 2\sqrt{3}t \\ z = 0 \end{cases}$$

CONCLUSIONS

The theorem. Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_r be smooth vector fields on a manifold M . Then the system $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_r\}$ is integrable if and only if it is in involution.

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